

GIDROTEXNIKA QURILISHIDA YER ISHLARINI HAJMINI ANIQLASH.

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Annotatsiya: *Gidrotexnika qurilishida yer ishlarini hajmini aniqlashda bir nechta formulalardan foydalanish mumkin. Agar kotlavan to'g'ri to'rtburchak shaklida bo'lsa grunt hajmini aniqlash uchun prizmatoid formulasi, ko'pburchak shaklidagi kotlavan bo'lsa Simpson formulasi va shunga o'xshash formulalardan foydalanish mumkin.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *Gidrotexnika inshootlari, kotlavan, hajm, prizmatoid, grunt, kanallar, dambalar, xandaq.*

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ОБЪЕМОВ ЗЕМЛЯНЫХ РАБОТ В ГИДРОТЕХНИЧЕСКОМ СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВЕ.

Абстрактный: *Для определения объема земляных работ в гидротехническом строительстве можно использовать несколько формул. Если яма прямоугольной формы, для определения объема почвы можно использовать формулу призматоида, если яма многоугольная, то можно использовать формулу Симпсона и подобные формулы.*

Ключевые слова: *Гидротехнические сооружения, котлован, объем, призматомид, грунт, каналы, плотины, траншея.*

DETERMINING THE VOLUME OF EARTHWORK IN HYDRAULIC ENGINEERING CONSTRUCTION.

Abstract: *Several formulas can be used to determine the volume of earthworks in hydraulic engineering construction. If the pit is rectangular, the prismatoid formula can be used to determine the soil volume, if the pit is polygonal, Simpson's formula and similar formulas can be used.*

Key words: *Hydrotechnical structures, excavation, volume, prismatoid, soil, canals, dams, trench.*

Gidrotexnika inshootlari har xil shakllarga ega bo'ladi. Shu bois ularni bir qancha shaklan sodda uchastkalarga va elementlarning hajmlariga ajratish, ulardan har birining maydoni va hajmini alohida aniqlash, so'ngra ularni qo'shib, butun inshoot maydoni va hajmini aniqlash lozim.

To'g'ri to'rtburchak shakldagi, raxli kotlovandan 1-rasm, a) olinadigan grunt hajmi prizmatoid formulasi yordamida aniqlanadi:

$$V = [ab + cd + (a + c)(b + d)] H / 6$$

bu erda: a va b – kotlovan tubidagi taraflarning kattaligi, m; c va d – kotlovan sirtidagi taraflarning kattaligi, m; H – kotlovan chuqurligi, m.

Tubi va usti joyda ko'pburchak shaklidagi kotlovandan (1-rasm) b) olinadigan grunt hajmi Simpson formulasi yordamida aniqlanadi:

$$V = (F_1 + F_2 + 4F_{o'rt}) H / 6$$

bu erda: F₁ va F₂ – kotlovan tubi va ustining yuzasi, m²; F_{o'rt} – kotlovan

balandligining o'rtasi darajasida aniqlanadigan kotlov qirg'irining yuzasi, u F_1 va F_2 ning o'rtacha qiymati sifatida emas, balki uning amaldagi o'lchamlariga ko'ra aniqlanadi, m^2 .

Tubi va usti joyda kvadrat shaklida hamda raxlarining qiyaligi bir xil bo'lgan kotlovandan olinadigan grunt hajmi ag'darilgan qirg'ilgan piramida formulasi yordamida aniqlanadi:

$$V = (F_1 + F_2 + (F_1 F_2)^{1/2}) H / 3,$$

Ag'darilgan qirg'ilgan konus shaklidagi kotlovandan (v) olinadigan grunt hajmi quyidagi formula yordamida aniqlanadi:

$$V = (R^2 + r^2 + Rr) \pi H / 3,$$

bu yerda: R va r – kotlovan tubi va ustining radiuslari, m.

Qazilmalar va ko'tarmalarning sxemalari (1-rasm)

Tasmasimon uzunlikdagi inshootlar (kanallar, dambalar, xandaqlar va b)da (g , d) grunt hajmi taxminan quyidagi formula bo'yicha aniqlanadi:

$$V = (F_1 + F_2) l / 2$$

bu yerda: F_1 va F_2 – inshootlarning bo'ylama kesimi singan nuqtalarda ularning ikki chekkadagi ko'ndalang qirg'irlarining yuzasi, m^2 ; l – bu qirg'irlar o'rtasidagi uchastkaning uzunligi, m. Hisoblab topilgan hajm amaldagidan kattaroq bo'ladi.

Aniqroq hisob-kitoblar uchun Vinkler formulasidan foydalaniladi:

$$V = [(F_1 + F_2) / 2 - m (H_1 - H_2)^2 / 6] l$$

bu yerda: m – raxlarning joylashish koeffitsienti; H – inshootlar qirg'irlarining chuqurligi yoki balandligi, m.

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